

Comparison of PCR and Phenotypic Methods for the Detection of Methicillin Resistant Staphylococcus Aureus

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: - First, *S. aureus* infections caused by penicillin-resistant *S. aureus* were treated with methicillin in 1959. The United Kingdom reported that *S. aureus* isolates had developed methicillin resistance (Methicillin-Resistant *S. aureus*) and numerous MRSA isolates were subsequently reported from other European nations as well as Japan, Australia, and the United States. Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) is known to be resistant to several different antibiotic classes.

AIM:-To compare conventional methods for MRSA detection with the Molecular approach of detecting *mecA* gene through PCR for accuracy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: -This study was conducted in the Department of Microbiology IMCH&RC, Indore for 18 months. Clinical samples from OPD/IPD were collected and processed by standard procedures and AST was performed according to the CLSI 2024. The MRSA species were examined for Cefoxitin susceptibility by the Disc Diffusion (DD) method and E test for the detection of Minimal Inhibitory Concentration (MIC). The drug-resistant gene *mecA* was detected by conventional PCR.

RESULT: - Out of 110 isolates, 45 isolates of MRSA were found to be Cefoxitin Resistance by Disc Diffusion (Kirby Baur's) Method. The Prevalence of MRSA was found by DD method for the detection of 45/110 (40.91%) and E test by 40/110 (36.3%) in the present study. The molecular characterization confirms 36/40 MRSA for the *mecA* gene.

CONCLUSION:- The prevalence MRSA for the *mecA* gene among was observed to be 32.7%. Prolonged hospital stay and direct antibiotic pressure in the hospital can lead to the development of MRSA variants.

Keywords: MRSA, Disc Diffusion method, E- test, PCR .

INTRODUCTION

Microbes are found in the environment and are beneficial to all aspects of life. Microorganisms in the environment control a number of biological processes to varying degrees. Numerous microorganisms, including bacteria, viruses, mycoplasma, protozoans, and others, are known to have both positive and harmful effects on humans and other living things (1).

Staphylococcus aureus (*S. aureus*), one of the well-known bacteria, is endangering human health in a number of ways. Human *S. aureus* infection rates are significantly greater in various infections (2). Worldwide, hospital and community-acquired infections are primarily caused by *S. aureus*(3).

Gram's-positive cocci, or *S. aureus*, are non-motile, non-spore-forming bacteria that are shaped like grape clusters and have a diameter of around 1 μ m. The most prevalent cause of localized supportive lesions in humans is *S. aureus*. It originated from a particular subspecies of *Aureus* that produced colonies on solid media that were golden in color. It is widely known that *S. aureus* can induce a wide range of pyogenic lesions in many organs, mostly in hospital and community-acquired infections (4).

First, *S. aureus* infections caused by penicillin-resistant *S. aureus* were treated with methicillin in 1959. The United Kingdom reported that *S. aureus* isolates had developed methicillin resistance (Methicillin-Resistant *S. aureus*) (5), and numerous MRSA isolates were subsequently reported from other European nations as well as Japan, Australia, and the United States (6). Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) is known to be resistant to several different antibiotic classes. Due of colonization or transmission from one person to another, especially through the hands of colonized healthcare personnel, it has mostly spread in hospitals (7). Numerous infections, including those of the urinary system, lungs, and bones and joints, have been linked to MRSA leading to endo-carditis and osteo-myelitis. (8-9)

The spread of MRSA was also significantly influenced by polluted environmental surfaces. Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (CA-MRSA), another MRSA strain, has raised serious concerns about public health (10). It's difficult to distinguish between hospital-acquired MRSA (IIA-MRSA) and community-acquired MRSA (CA-MRSA). Because it has been discovered that CA-MRSA frequently spreads to hospitals as well. (10)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted in the Department of Microbiology at IMCH&RC, Indore for 24 months (Feb 2024 to Feb 2026). Total 110 Clinical samples from OPD/IPD were collected and processed by standard procedures and AST was performed according to the CLSI 2024. The MRSA species were examined for Cefoxitin susceptibility by the Disc Diffusion (DD) method and E test for the detection of Minimal Inhibitory Concentration (MIC). The drug resistant gene *mecA* was detected by conventional PCR.

Identification of *S. aureus*: - Blood agar and mannitol salt agar have been used to cultivate the microbially infected specimens (Hi Media, India). Using a variety of techniques, including colony morphology, Gram's staining, the catalase test, slide and tube coagulase, and mannitol, *S. aureus* was identified and distinguished from related species. test for antibiotic susceptibility and fermentation.

Antimicrobial Sensitivity Testing: Antibiotic sensitivity was performed for all the isolates by Kirby- Bauer disc diffusion method using Cation adjusted Mueller – Hinton agar plates. The panel of drugs used for antimicrobial sensitivity testing was Gentamicin, Amikacin, Vancomycin, Ciprofloxacin, Teicoplanin, Cefoxitin, Amoxicillin, Penicillin.

MIC determination of MRSA: Oxacillin MIC testing was done with E-Strip (Hi-Media, Oxacillin EZY MIC strip 0.016-256mcg/ml) with a 0.5 McFarland inoculum, as per the directions provided by the manufacturer. Mueller-Hinton agar (MHA) plates with 2% NaCl were used. A lawn culture of a standardized bacterial suspension was applied to the MHA plate with a sterile cotton swab. The E-strip with preformed antibiotic gradient, was immediately placed on the agar surface. The plate was kept in incubation at 35°C for 24 hours. The CLSI criteria categorise *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates as *methicillin-susceptible (MSSA)* if the Oxacillin MIC is <2µg/ml and *methicillin-resistant (MRSA)* if the MIC is >4 µg/ml.

Detection of Gene responsible for MRSA :*mecA* genes were detected according to standard protocol which includes:

All suspected MRSA isolates were confirmed by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and subsequent agarose gel electrophoresis, which is the gold standard test. A DNA extraction kit containing a spin column and an amplification kit for PCR and agarose gel electrophoresis was purchased from HELINI Biomolecules, Chennai. The amplification kit consisted of forward and reverse primers for *mecA*, 5' GTT GAA ATG ACT GAA CGT CCCG ATA A 3' and 5' CCA ATT CCA CAT TGT TTC GGT CTA A 3', which would yield an amplification product of 310 kbp. Each PCR tube contained a 15-µl master mix and 5-µl extracted DNA. PCR conditions were initial annealing at 95°C for 5 min, denaturation at 95°C for 45 s, annealing at 54°C for 45 s, extension at 72°C for 30 s for 35 cycles, and final extension at 72°C for 3 min. Next, 20 µl of each sample, 15 µl of negative control, and 15 µl of positive control were loaded onto a 1% agarose gel containing ethidium bromide. A 100-bp molecular weight ladder was used to identify the amplified product. (11-19)

RESULTS

Graph No.1: Out of 110, *S. aureus* clinical samples (65 MSSA & 45 MRSA) (such as blood and pus) were seen, and each sample was screened for the different strains of aureus as indicated.

Graph no. 2 : Gender wise distribution of MRSA isolates

shows gender wise distribution out of 45, MRSA isolates in which males were found more infected 32 than females 13.

Graph no. 3. Specimen wise distribution of MSSA & MRSA isolates.

shows that maximum no. of infection of *S. aureus* was found in the pus of the patients while minimum no. of infection of *S. aureus* was observed in the blood of the patients

Table no. 1. Detection of MRSA by Disk diffusion & E test (MIC)

<i>S. aureus</i> strains	Disc diffusion test (cx,ox)	E-test (MICTest)
MRSA	45	40
Total	45	40

Table

no. 1 The E- test were also used in this investigation to screen for Staphylococcal strains. The disc diffusion test was used to confirm the MRSA, which was 45 (CX, OX), and the E-test was used to confirm the MRSA which was 40.isolates,

Graph no. 4. Antibiotics sensitivity pattern of S.aureus (N= 110)

The accompanying table displays the antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of 110 strains throughout this investigation. The MRSA isolates that were gathered had the highest rates of susceptibility to linezolid (100%), teicoplanin (100%), and tetracycline (81.2 %).

Table No.2: Comparison of MRSA Detection by Disc diffusion Method and E test Method. (n=45)

MRSA	DETECTION	NOT DETECTION	TOTAL	Chi-square test value	p-value
Disc diffusion Method	45	65	110	10.861	0.001
E test Method.	40	70	110		

Among the 110 isolates, Disc diffusion (Kirby Baures) method, was used to confirm the MRSA isolate 45 (40.9%) and E test method isolates were discovered to be MRSA 40 (36.3%) producers.

Table no.3 . Detection of gene from MRSA detect by E -test

Gene	No. of Isolates Confirms the presence of gene
Mec A gene	34
Others Gene	06
Total	40

In this research. The molecular analysis was performed on MRSA isolates. 40, isolates yielded high-quality DNA. Here, gel pictures of a few DNA samples were displayed. The investigation found the Mec A gene in 34 MRSA isolate and 6 MRSA isolates having other genes.

DISCUSSION

A total of 1970 samples from all of North India were gathered for this study. Only 110 *S. aureus* were found for additional processing following microbiological screening. In order to identify MRSA strains in the northern Indian region, particularly in the Indore zone, this study used microbiological, biochemical, and molecular biological techniques. The MRSA strains under study have a great propensity to cause soft tissue infections, biofilm formation, and serious skin damage in the local population. The utilization of potential antibiotics to treat the afflicted population has been shown by this investigation. There were 45 MRSA strains in all 110, *S. aureus* isolates included in this investigation. Of the 45 MRSA isolates, 45 were found to be Disc diffusion test positive, 40 were proven to be E test. Similar study was found Deyno S et al (20)

The age group of 41–50 years old (males) had the highest number of isolates in this study, whereas the age group above 61 years old (females) had the lowest. According to this data, the average mean age of *S. aureus* strain growth cases was found to be greater than the average mean age of the population. The following table lists similar types of discoveries that have been documented in the literature like Bhimrao et al. (21)

In the present study out of 110 isolates, 45 (40.9 %) were found to be MRSA by Disc Diffusion method and E test by 40/110 (36.3%). Supportive results were seen in a study conducted by George C.R.R. *et al.* (22) Another study which showed similar observation was conducted by tay or T A *et al.* (23) which reported the MRSA prevalence to be 42% & 44 % respectively.

The study employed the disc diffusion test to ascertain the pattern of antibiotic sensitivity. The resistance and sensitivity zone that were achieved are recorded. We looked at how sensitive all methicillin-resistant staphylococci were to commonly used medications. It was shown that every MRSA isolate was responsive to linezolid, teicoplanin, and vancomycin but resistant to oxacillin and cefoxitin. The battle against MRSA is made more difficult by the emergence of resistance to other antibiotic classes, which drastically limits the available treatment options. Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* is becoming increasingly common in both hospital and community settings. Supportive results were seen in a study conducted by kanji lal S et al (24) and Gurung R et al.(25)

Throughout the experiment, genomic DNA was collected and PCR was set up to identify the MecA gene in the *S. aureus* isolates. For the MecA gene, positive gene controls were supplied by ATCC USA, while negative controls were isolated using the DNA of healthy individuals. For study authentication, each sample (tests and controls) was arranged in a triplet. The MRSA isolates used in this study were found to carry the MecA gene. The identification of the MecA gene in 34 MRSA isolates out of 40 confirmed that the strains were *S. aureus* isolates because this gene is a characteristic of *S. aureus* and rest 6 MRSA isolates having other than mec A gene. Similar findings have been reported by several writers, like Chai M H et al (26) and Wan Y et al (27).

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